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Advancing evolutionary economic geography by engaged pluralism

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Abstract

Since 2006 economic geographers have been confronted with attempts to constitute a new paradigm of evolutionary economic geography. This paper aims at advancing evolutionary economic geography by reviewing its core critique and proposed solutions, particularly that of integrating the perspective of a geographical political economy. Although we sympathize with the identified shortcomings of evolutionary economic geography, we regard the proposed alternative approach, geographical political economy, as too narrow and reductionist. By combining evolutionary and relational economic geography in certain respects we plead for advancing evolutionary economic geography by engaged pluralism.

Evolutionary economic geography, Sympathetic critique, Relational economic geography,
Engaged pluralism

Hassink, R., Klaerding, C. und Marques, P. „*Engaged Pluralism*“ als Beitrag zur Weiterentwicklung der evolutionären Wirtschaftsgeographie

Seit 2006 gibt es unter Wirtschaftsgeographen Bemühungen ein neues Paradigma der evolutionären Wirtschaftsgeographie zu etablieren. Dieser Artikel verfolgt das Ziel einen Beitrag zu dieser Debatte zu leisten und damit die evolutionäre Wirtschaftsgeographie weiterzuentwickeln. Dazu werden bestehende Kritikpunkte an evolutionären Ansätzen und dafür vorgesehene Lösungsansätze, speziell die Integration verschiedener Perspektiven der politischen Wirtschaftsgeographie, untersucht. Obwohl wir die Erkenntnisse über die Defizite der evolutionären Wirtschaftsgeographie teilen, erachten wir den vorgeschlagenen alternativen Ansatz der politischen Wirtschaftsgeographie als zu begrenzt und reduktionistisch. Mittels der Kombination bestimmter Aspekte der relationalen und der evolutionären Wirtschaftsgeographie schlagen wir die Weiterentwicklung der evolutionären Wirtschaftsgeographie durch einen „*Engaged Pluralism*“ vor.

Evolutionäre Wirtschaftsgeographie, Relationale Wirtschaftsgeographie, Konstruktive Kritik,
Engaged Pluralism

Hassink, R., Klaerding, C., Marques, P. 以互动多元主义来推进演化经济地理学

自 2006 年以来，经济地理学者一直试图建立一个演化经济地理学新范式。本文对演化经济地理学存在的主要争议和相关解释进行回顾，特别是从融合了地理政治经济学的视角上，意在推进演化经济地理学的理论认识。尽管我们意识到了演化经济地理学所存在的不足之处，但将地理政治经济学作为推动演化经济地理学发展的新方法则显得过于狭隘和存在以偏概全之嫌。通过将关系经济地理学和演化经济地理学在一定程度上进行结合，我们认为通过此类的互动多元化的方式能够推进演化经济地理学的发展。

演化经济地理学，同情性批判，关系经济地理学，互动多元主义

JEL classifications: R1, R

1. Introduction

As several scholars have observed, human geography in general and economic geography in particular, is full of enthusiastic, but often superficial attempts to embrace theoretical thinking from neighbouring social and economic sciences (CLOKE and JOHNSTON, 2005; ALLEN et al., 1997; MASSEY et al., 1999; JONES, 2009; HAMNETT, 2003; SUNLEY, 2008; SCOTT, 2000).

What starts with the adoption of some ideas and notions to explain phenomena, sometimes ends with a so-called turn in the discipline or the proposal of a new paradigm. Since 2006 economic geographers have been confronted with the attempt to constitute such a new paradigm within their field of study, namely evolutionary economic geography (EEG) (BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2006, 2011; BOSCHMA and MARTIN, 2007, 2010; FRENKEN, 2007).

EEG deals with “the processes by which the economic landscape—the spatial organization of economic production, distribution and consumption—is transformed over time” (BOSCHMA and MARTIN, 2007, p. 539). Although economic geographers, particularly members of the Californian school (STORPER and WALKER, 1989), have worked with evolutionary notions in the past (see also GRABHER, 1993), since 2006 EEG has been constituted as a paradigm in a more systematic and comprehensive way. The paper by BOSCHMA and FRENKEN (2006) has become a particular reference point – evident not least in terms of its citations – in proposing the ontological and epistemological paradigm of EEG.

Although EEG’s future seems to be promising, it has nonetheless been criticised for the strong emphasis on organisational routines, thereby relegating the role of institutions as well as under-conceptualizing social agency and power (PIKE et al., 2009). This paper aims to contribute to the theoretical advancement of EEG by reviewing this core critiques and proposed solutions, particularly that of integrating this perspective with geographical political

economy (from now on GPE) (MACKINNON et al., 2009; PIKE et al., 2009). We sympathise with some of the criticism but also evaluate GPE as too limited. In addition to GPE, we argue that EEG can be advanced by including ideas derived from institutional and relational economic geography.

In order to connect EEG to additional theoretical avenues we argue in favour of an engaged pluralism, an approach recently discussed by BARNES and SHEPPARD (2010) as a way to bring together the different perspectives that enrich Economic Geography. Based on dialogue, translation and what the authors call trading zones, engaged pluralism is necessary to advance the paradigm and to overcome its limitations. Although we take the proposed paradigm of EEG as a starting point of our discussion, we are against fragmented pluralism with paradigmatic boxes existing in isolation to each other. Although fragmented pluralism might be necessary to establish a paradigm, as BOSCHMA and FRENKEN (2006) have done by contrasting EEG with institutional economic geography and neoclassical economic geography, it leads to false dualisms (SHEPPARD and PLUMMER, 2007).

Our paper is organised in the following way: in order to clarify our arguments we summarize in section 2 the core characteristics of EEG and the main criticism levelled against it with respect to the low significance of institutions, the under-conceptualized notions of social agency and power as well as the neglected multi-scalar interrelatedness and embeddedness of firms . Section 3 deals with the proposed alternatives to overcome some of the limitations of EEG, namely geographical political economy, institutional economic geography and relational economic geography. The paper concludes by summarising how these alternatives can strengthen EEG through engaged pluralism (Section 4).

2. Introducing evolutionary economic geography

EEG has attracted much attention in economic geography, both theoretically and increasingly also empirically, as documented by the number of publications in English (BOSCHMA and MARTIN, 2010; SCHAMP, 2005, 2012; HASSINK, 2010; CHO and HASSINK, 2009; HENNING et al., 2013; ESSLETZBICHLER, 2012) in Chinese (LIU et al., 2011; WANG et al., 2013), special issues (HASSINK and SHIN, 2005; BOSCHMA and MARTIN, 2007; GRABHER, 2009), edited books (SHAPIRA and FUCHS, 2005; FRENKEN, 2007; BOSCHMA and MARTIN, 2010), workshops, such as in Cambridge and Jena (at the Max Planck Institute of Economics) as well as special sessions at the Global Conference on Economic Geography in Beijing and at AAG Annual Meetings.

Moreover, evolutionary thinking has been applied to define and improve existing theoretical concepts in economic geography, such as regional innovation systems (COOKE, 2004; UYARRA, 2010) clusters (STABER, 2010; MENZEL and FORNAHL, 2010), to reflect on its implications for regional policy (BOSCHMA, 2008; HASSINK and KLAERDING, 2011) and to explain spatial evolution in new industries, such as tourism (MA and HASSINK, 2013) and creative industries (BERG and HASSINK, 2013). SCOTT (2000, p. 494), in his seminal overview of economic geography theorising, clearly indicates the influence of evolutionary thinking on current research in economic geography. The increased importance of EEG can finally be underlined by The Times Higher Education Index where ‘relational and evolutionary economic geography’ ranks third by the number of citations in social sciences journals (COE, 2011, p. 82).

2.1 Characteristics of evolutionary economic geography

EEG aims to explain the emergence and changes in economic landscapes by the underlying industrial dynamics of firms (BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2009, p. 152; BOSCHMA and MARTIN, 2010, p. 25). It aims to tackle research objectives addressed to different spatial levels, which, in our view, represent the research scope of contemporary economic geography (BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2006, p. 293, 295): on the micro-level the decision-making and location behaviour of *firms* are analysed; the spatial evolution of *sectors* and the co-evolution of firms, technologies and local or regional institutions are focused at the meso-level, whereas the convergence or divergence in spatial systems such as *regions or nations* is subject to the analysis on the macro-level.

The major terms and concepts of EEG are derived from evolutionary economics, generalized Darwinism and complexity theory which highlight, amongst others, the roles of path dependence, variety, selection and organizational routines for regional development and adjustment (BOSCHMA and LAMBOUY, 1999; COE, 2011). Based on NELSON and WINTER's (1982) evolutionary theory of economic change, and contrary to alternative approaches such as institutional economic geography (from here on IEG) or neoclassical economics, for BOSCHMA and MARTIN (2007, p. 541) *routines* are the key: they coordinate and control firm behaviour and thereby shape distinctive competitive advantages at the micro-level which unfold onto other spatial layers through processes of interaction.

In contrast, territorial institutions are argued to affect industrial dynamics only weakly, hence opposing central assumptions of institutional approaches to economic geography (BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2006, 2009). They are attached to the meso- and macro-level of economic landscapes (SCHAMP, 2005, p. 618-619) and perceived as more durable compared to the rather

temporary, more dynamic organisational routines (ESSLETZBICHLER, 2009). The marginal role of institutions, for instance materialized as industrial relations or technology standards, is considered to result from its “too loose”, “nonbinding” and “so general” characteristics (BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2009, pp. 152-153); differences in institutional frames, as argued from an institutional perspective, would not sufficiently explain intra-regional variety of local networking activities or the replication of the same routines across national institutional boundaries.

The weak influence of institutions on the spatial formation of new industries is discussed in the concept of windows of locational opportunity (STORPER and WALKER, 1989) which is based on evolutionary thought. Since sector-specific institutions are assumed to only co-evolve with new industries, existing institutional endowments such as general knowledge, skills, service providers or a reliable judicial system are not expected to match new industrial requirements. In this view such basic institutions seem to be too widely available in space to adequately explain the evolution of new industrial regions (BOSCHMA and LAMBOOY, 1999, p. 423; BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2009, p. 155).

Closely connected to analysing emerging industries is the notion of industrial decline and regional lock-in. EEG assumes that established spatial patterns tend to be largely irreversible due to their path-dependent evolution. Lock-in situations appear because specialized industrial regions endowed with particular resources, competences and institutional structures are unable to adapt to changing market requirements; also, built-up agglomeration economies with respect to infrastructure and services hinder renewal processes (BOSCHMA and LAMBOOY, 1999, p. 418; MARTIN and SUNLEY, 2006, p. 409). However, the main argument from an EEG perspective is, again, focussed on the firm level. Organisational routines shaping the learning and creative capability of firms and whole industries are dangerously limited because they do not fit to the new situation any longer whereas, at the same time, the internal selection process

fails due to consolidated routines regarding problem solving (BOSCHMA and LAMBOUY, 1999, p. 416).

Nonetheless, institutions are ascribed some relevance for economic change, namely in the process of co-evolution. "If institutions play a role, it will be more often in an endogenous manner as entrepreneurial firms, consumers and government officials engage in collective action to establish new institutions" (BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2009, p. 5). BATHELT and BOGGS (2003, p. 278), for instance, take such an approach to explain regional development through interactive learning. "Thus, interactive learning is concerned not only with creating technological and organizational innovations (...), but with creating wider institutions that circulate capital in all its forms. Thus, regional development paths take place within a wider social context." Regional actors are hence, challenged to shape their own capabilities to adjust and (re-)invent industrial and economic structures, for example by rebundling local resources which had previously been neglected (BATHELT and BOGGS, 2003, pp. 276-77). The co-evolution of institutions, technologies and sectors contributes to the transformation of previously 'neutral' places, endowed with generic factors, into 'real' places (BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2006, p. 291). This is in contrast to an institutional approach which argues from existing institutional differences, thereby, assuming 'real' places as a starting point for regional economic analyses but fatally neglecting the processes of emergence (BOSCHMA and FRENKEN, 2006, p. 277).

Empirical research in EEG has been concentrated on three main areas, according to BOSCHMA and FRENKEN (2011). The first is research on clusters, with a particular emphasis on the path dependent nature of their evolution and the internal dynamics of clusters, which make them likely to emerge and remain in place even if localisation economies do not materialise. Their existence is a result of spin-off activities with localisation economies playing only a limited role in this process. The second line of research revolves around specialisation versus

diversification. Specialisation argues that positive externalities benefit firms located in an economic agglomeration. A second line of argument, influenced by the work of JACOBS (1970), argues that diversity is essential for innovation and creativity. EEG has gone beyond this dichotomy to argue that the crucial point is the right balance between cognitive distance and proximity that allow for innovation and interaction. This is encapsulated in the concept of related variety. EEG has also argued that agglomeration externalities are likely to be dependent on the stage of the product lifecycle in an industry and at the micro-level on the characteristics of each firm. Finally, and despite EEG's general neglect of institutions, some research has already been done on the role of institutions on the evolution of regional development, mostly regarding their capacity (or lack thereof) to co-evolve and adapt to changing economic circumstances.

2.1 The limitations of evolutionary economic geography

In this paper we will highlight three of main limitations that have been identified within EEG approaches: first, *the limited importance attached to institutions*; secondly, *the under-conceptualized notion of social agency and power*; and thirdly, *the neglected multi-scalar interrelatedness and embeddedness of firms* (PIKE et al., 2009; MACKINNON et al., 2009). Regarding the first point, it is a direct consequence of BOSCHMA and FRENKEN's (2006) attempt to draw a clear line between evolutionary and institutional theory, which led them to emphasise that the first should not be primarily concerned with institutions. This distinction would however always be prone to criticism, since many applications of evolutionary theory had emphasised the importance of institutions (COOKE et al., 1998; HODGSON, 2004). While many economic geographers would agree that institutions matter for regional development

(RODRÍGUEZ-POSE, 2013; GERTLER, 2010, p. 3), MACKINNON et al. (2009, p. 135) reveal that, in contrast, “some of the recent contributions to EEG have risked relegating the role of institutions in shaping processes of economic change. (...) There seems to be little interest in how institutions are actually constructed and endure over time, which requires a deeper engagement with older institutionalist conceptions of instincts, habit, language, and power”.

The notion of a layered ontology, for example, derived from Generalised Darwinism, argues that institutions emerge out of the complex interactions between individuals and organisations to form an upper level of society which is not reducible to its individual components (HODGSON, 2004). At the same time, these institutions influence and constrain the decisions of agents, through a process of downward causation. The use of the layer metaphor does not imply a form of hierarchical power between levels – rather it points to the wide and pervasive influence that institutions have over simpler forms of social life, like a mantle that stands above the decisions of individuals. More recently, MARTIN and SUNLEY (2014), reviewing recent developments in biology and evolutionary theory, suggested that a greater emphasis on this dimension of analysis is essential to achieve the deep contextualisation that both the biological and social sciences have concluded to be important in explaining evolution.

We therefore argue that a *broader approach to institutions* is needed, one which emphasises its strong impact on individual agency (HODGSON, 2009), expands beyond the firm-level and acknowledges the entanglement of various scales instead of conceptualizing an almost linear relationship between organisational routines and institutions (PIKE et al., 2009, p. 179; MACKINNON et al., 2009, p. 140). Some evolutionary economic geographers even largely ignore the institutional environment and its influence on firms. This line of work has for example focused on the study of spin-off dynamics and the transmission of successful routines from mother companies to their spin out companies, e.g. in the car industry or fashion design industry (KLEPPER, 2007; WENTING, 2008). By doing this they ignore that

firms in these locations can probably develop successful internal routines thanks to the favourable institutional environment (specialised labour market, training institutions, innovative or creative milieu etc.), something that might not be available in other locations.

EEG has also overlooked the *role of power* in shaping economic outcomes (JONES, 2008, p. 72; MACKINNON et al., 2009, p. 137; PIKE et al., 2009, p. 180). Induced by different capacities of agents to enforce interests or access information, power is regarded as a crucial source of uneven social and economic development. Power can be understood in several ways, ranging from structuralist Marxist perspectives, for whom power is the preserve of the ruling class due to its control of the means of production, to post-structuralist approaches, that see power as immanent and performative, that is only effective to the extent that individuals (both those exercising power and those being subject to it) choose to reproduce it.

ALLEN'S (2003, 2004) seminal work on power and geography sought to bridge these opposing views, arguing that power is a relational effect that results from the capacity to mobilise the resources available to individuals and organisations. Therefore the size of an organisation, for example, is likely to influence its capacity to exercise power. At the same time, power does not flow unobstructed through time and space to produce a perfectly determined outcome; instead it is subject to several opposing and even contradictory forces that constantly challenge its original intentions and modify it. Crucially, power can be exercised through several mechanisms, such as coercion, charisma, leadership or persuasion, among others.

Going back to our original point, an excessive focus on firm level routines is likely to obscure how the unequal distribution of economic resources through space is *also* a result of power dynamics. Firms, public sector organisations, trade unions, NGOs or individuals can use the resources available to them to achieve their strategic goals sometimes at the expense of others. This can happen both through conflict or collaboration, on the basis of coercion or in a more

benign way through the mobilisation of regional resources to become more innovative and therefore less replaceable. It is not a unidirectional nor simple tale of big versus small, but it is however an element that must not be ignored in order to capture fully the dynamics of evolutionary processes.

Finally, our third point is the neglect of the multi-scalar interrelatedness and embeddedness of firms in the EEG framework. As argued above, EEG explains spatial economic outcomes on the meso- and macro-level from the micro-behaviour of firms, thus relegating the influence of other spatial scales. Privileging the firm as an initiator of economic change neglects the importance of other actors such as the state, labour and civic society groups and leads to *losing sight of the positioning of firms in wider networks, processes and structures*, such as the embeddedness in global production networks (MACKINNON et al., 2009, p. 139). As we pointed out in our discussion of the importance of institutions and power, these multiple connections and interdependencies are crucial if we are to achieve a comprehensive framework with which to explain economic evolution. Both firms and institutions operate on multiple scales (HASSINK and KLAERDING, 2012). The first through their connections, collaborations or location decisions often need to deal with local/regional externalities, national and international regulation and the effects of globalised markets. Institutions (formal and informal) on the other hand, exist on multiple scales, from the local to the international.

In conclusion, we agree with the outlined critique on EEG, particularly the ones related to institutions and real places. On the one hand, we believe it necessary to broaden the “reductionist” and “incomplete” understanding of institutions currently applied within EEG (PIKE et al., 2009, p. 179); on the other hand, we sympathise with its focus on “the processes and mechanisms by which the economy *self-transforms itself from within*” (BOSCHMA and MARTIN, 2010, p. 4, italics in original) reinforcing the capability of firms to create ‘real’ places. In order to discuss and advance our understanding of evolutionary processes in the

next section we evaluate the potential contributions to EEG of three alternative approaches, namely GPE, institutional economic geography (IEG) and relational economic geography (REG).

3. Advancing evolutionary economic geography by engaged pluralism

There are several alternatives to draw upon to start addressing the criticisms highlighted above. Several recent critics of EEG suggest GPE as the main alternative (MACKINNON et al., 2009; PIKE et al., 2009), though as indicated in the introduction of this paper, there are other paradigms with interesting concepts and insights that can compensate for the limitations of EEG; namely institutional economic geography (IEG) and relational economic geography (REG). Both are regarded as neighbouring paradigms, turns or theories because they tend to have an implicit or explicit evolutionary bent (Figure 1). For example in their conceptual paper on REG, BATHELT and GLÜCKLER (2003, p. 134) define evolution as an important constitutive element of their framework alongside organisation, innovation and interaction. Regarding GPE, the design of economies is explained by its “spatialized social relations, social agency, and socio-institutional context *over time, across space, and in place*” (PIKE, 2006, p. 206, italics by authors). A similar point can be made for IEG (see for example GERTLER, 2010).

- Insert Figure 1 here The pedigree of theories of economic geography and related disciplines¹

In the following section we will first explain what GPE stands for and how it can overcome some of the limitations of EEG. We will then introduce two additional approaches in economic geography, institutional and relational economic geography, and will elaborate on their potential in overcoming limitations of EEG.

3.1 Geographical Political Economy

GPE is a term that can include a variety of approaches, as illustrated by SHEPPARD (2011) who uses it as an umbrella for several trends within Economic Geography. Nonetheless, in the definition of MACKINNON et al. (2009) and MARTIN and SUNLEY (2014) GPE is summarised as a theoretical framework concerned with the relationships between the state, labour and capital and the inherent tendency of capitalism to generate uneven territorial development. Contrary to more recent perspectives that tend to privilege the contingent, temporary and relational nature of economic development, GPE argues that there are core contradictions within capitalism that operate across a variety of geographical scales. It does not deny that there is variation at the local level, but merely that it happens within a wider political-economic regulatory regime. According to both COE (2011) and MARTIN and SUNLEY (2014), EEG would benefit from stronger engagement with GPE, due to the latter's emphasis on

uneven territorial development, power, and the role of institutions. However we do not endorse this position, as explained in the following sections, and instead suggest that both IEG and REG would be better suited for this task.

In terms of its research applications, GPE tends to privilege the impact of external investment on regional development, or the power asymmetries between transnational corporations and local firms. An example is given by PIKE (2006). Using the case study of a brewery located in Sunderland, in the North East of England, the author demonstrates how the loss of local ownership, together with financialization and the supremacy of shareholder value led to the closure of an important local asset. It highlights both the economic and geographical dimension of the relationship between financial capital and its investments, arguing that the values and logic of this geographically concentrated sector (finance) supported by its corporate power were able to override the interests of local stakeholders. Among the latter were the management team at the time, who offered their holding company a management buy-out solution to keep the firm open, which was denied because it did not satisfy the interests of the parent company.

Regarding institutions, GPE primarily thinks of capital-labour relations and the state regularities as those with the most influence on the evolution of territorial disparities (MACKINNON et al., 2009, p. 131). In the past, similar approaches such as the social relations of production (SRP) framework of the late 1970s were accused of overemphasizing the structural determination of territorial dynamics (YEUNG, 2005). According to SAYER (1995) this narrow delimitation of institutions, and its deterministic view about the relationship between capitalist relations and spatial structures, was responsible for the decline of radical political economy in the 1980s and 1990s. Despite recent attempts to engage in a more nuanced fashion with the role of institutions, in comparison with the SRP framework, GPE might struggle to engage theoretically with EEG, since the latter tends to pay greater attention

to context and variety. At the same time, it is important to identify a set of key institutions, even if on an abstract and general level, in order to guide empirical work and to allow comparisons between case studies. Therefore even if EEG does not adopt the same conception of state, labour and capital as the 'holy trinity' of territorial development, it would benefit from further attempts at clarification of what institutions are more important in framing economic activity.

The incorporation of power in terms of capital-labour conflicts and class by a GPE perspective (MACKINNON et al., 2009; PIKE et al., 2009) has been criticised as being too vague (HODGSON, 2009) and also, too limited to explain economic landscapes: “Although class is a central category and capital-labour conflict is the key driver of change in a political economy framework, it is one of many progenitors of change in evolutionary theory” (ESSLETZBICHLER, 2009, p. 163). We agree with the shortcoming and, again, refer to the specialised focus of GPE in contrast to a broader, more comprehensive perspective of power in a relational framework. In his seminal work on power and geography, ALLEN (2003, 2004) argues that despite attempts at theoretical clarification, structuralist approaches (in which we would include GPE) still tend to adopt a deterministic view of power that leads to descriptions of ‘capital’ acting to produce specific outcomes, ignoring the multiplicity and complexity of power relations in a real economy.

This view might be slightly outdated, as recent work under the GPE framework (as illustrated by PIKE 2006 cited above) has clearly attempted to break free from the restrictive mould of deterministic power relations. A recent paper by MACKINNON (2012) bringing together research on strategic coupling and GPE also makes clear statements regarding the need to avoid a simplistic view of power relations. Nonetheless more empirical work will still be necessary to demonstrate clearly how a neo-Marxist emphasis on state-labour relationships as

the core process explaining economic evolution can avoid relying on fixed power hierarchies and incorporate a more nuanced view of context and multi-scalar relationships.

Finally, in contrast to EEG, the multiple scales of activity are clearly defined by GPE as the state, trade regimes, labour and class. A positive result of this emphasis is that authors working under the GPE or similar frameworks, such as regulation theory, have often been among the first to highlight the continued relevance of the nation-state (MACKINNON et al., 2009; JESSOP, 2002). This has helped counteract some of the narratives about hyper-globalisation that have come both from critics and supporters (DICKEN, 2007). However, although PIKE et al. (2009, p. 128) argue that these scales are sufficient “to dissect the causal relations, mechanisms, and processes that matter to our explanation” we still perceive them as too narrow and reductionist. Institutions are neglected such as the cultural and cognitive embeddedness of actors (ZUKIN and DIMAGGIO, 1990, pp. 15-23) which are regarded as crucial sources for explaining economic behaviour within institutionalist theory (GERTLER, 2010). The concept of spatial divisions of labour popularised by MASSEY (1995) did have a specific multi-scalar framework, since it emphasised the hierarchical economic relations between regions. Nonetheless it was still predominantly framed by a neo-Marxist focus on the same core institutions of capitalism, and is therefore unlikely to be enough for the deep contextualisation suggested by MARTIN and SUNLEY (2014).

3.2 Institutional Economic Geography

In order to enhance the role of institutions as complementary factors of influence on organisational routines we, along with other critics, suggest a stronger engagement between

institutional economic thinking and EEG. It will allow institutions at different spatial levels to receive more attention in general, thus complementing the firm-centred perspective of EEG, by emphasising how human agency is enabled and constrained by social structures and its representative formal and informal institutions (Section 2). SCHAMP (2007, p. 247) has also argued for relating EEG and IEG particularly on the notion of co-evolution. Hence, he elaborates on the point that has been described as most significant for bringing institutions back into an EEG framework (Section 2).

Recently GERTLER (2010) called for a revised institutional economic geography, because as he argues despite a few attempts to bring institutions into the realm of economic geography (MARTIN, 2000; AMIN, 2001) this area has been relatively neglected. A relevant point for this is the fact that both the old and new versions of IEG highlight “how individual institutions – as well as their interaction with other institutions – evolve and change over time” (GERTLER, 2010, p. 6). An institutional approach to economic geography aims to explain the transformation of economic landscapes through an analysis of how institutions change along a path dependent trajectory (MARTIN, 2000, p. 80; MARTIN, 2010, 2012). Path dependence, as defined by MACKINNON (2009, p. 499), is anchored in “institutional and evolutionary economics which highlights the influence of past decisions and experiences in shaping how economic actors respond to wider processes of economic change.”

According to GERTLER (2010) this revised IEG should be structured around four attributes: 1) more room for agency, to avoid overly structuralist interpretations of social change; 2) a focus on how institutions, alone or in interaction with other institutions, evolve and change, including both endogenous and exogenous change; 3) a stronger emphasis on geographical variation, namely through a better understanding of how different scales interact to produce a specific outcome, and finally, 4) IEG would benefit from greater variety in methodological approaches, with a special emphasis on comparative research projects. Particularly the first

three points mean that what GERTLER (2010) is proposing is in many ways what we have been arguing in this paper also, and therefore it would appear that IEG would provide an excellent field for EEG to engage with. The only missing element in this description is the role of power, which however could be subsumed under the first point (the importance of agency), through we argue that it would deserve a greater emphasis.

3.3 Relational Economic Geography

The aim of relational economic geography is “to formulate research questions which are associated with the analysis of economic relations using a geographical lens” (BATHELT and GLÜCKLER, 2003, p. 128). It can be seen as part of a broader set of streams of relational thinking within human geography (for an overview see JONES, 2009) and economic geography (see SUNLEY, 2008). For the sake of clarity and comparability, in this paper the main focus will be on the epistemological paradigm of relational economic geography as proposed by BATHELT and GLÜCKLER (2003, 2011, 2012, 2013), with critical realism providing the ontological and epistemological background. The focus will be much less on other ontological relational perspectives in economic geography, such as relational perspectives on globalisation (AMIN, 2002), global production networks (DICKEN et al., 2001; COE et al., 2008) and cities and regions (AMIN, 2004), which can be regarded as being part of the much broader relational turn in economic geography (SUNLEY, 2008). BATHELT and GLÜCKLER’s (2003, 2012) relational economic geography is a deliberate attempt to build up a new paradigm within economic geography, as they clearly distinguish this new paradigm from older paradigms, such as *Länderkunde* and regional science.

A relational perspective is argued to provide better concepts for *comprehensively* theorizing institutions, power, social agency and particularly the interrelatedness between scales (YEUNG, 2005; BATHELT and GLÜCKLER, 2003; BOGGS and RANTISI, 2003; SUNLEY, 2008). Its emergence coincides with major shifts in economic organization in terms of outsourcing, specialisation and increased interfirm linkages in a post-Fordist production system (BOGGS and RANTISI, 2003, p. 109). Thematic concepts gained attention that stressed the relational embeddedness of actors, firms and organizations in networks, e.g. global production networks (DICKEN et al., 2001; COE et al., 2008). At the same time knowledge creation in firms, temporary work organisations (projects) as well as a socio-cultural embeddedness of actors emerged as new research fields of economic geography (IBERT, 2008, p. 7). Altogether, YEUNG (2005, p. 42) identifies three categories of theoretical frameworks, namely relational assets, network embeddedness and relational scales, which constitute a thematic turn towards a REG.

REG considers formal and informal institutions as central influences on the evolution of industries and the development of regional economies. Special emphasis is placed on the embeddedness of firms and organisational structures in a wider network of social relations and institutions at different spatial scales (BATHELT and GLÜCKLER, 2003, pp. 131, 133). As YEUNG (2005) points out, relational assets such as institutional thickness, social capital and untraded interdependencies, all of them transcending firm levels, constitute the core themes of REG. Furthermore, applying a relational perspective highlights the significance of institutions for the rise of new sectors. For instance the new media cluster in Leipzig developed not only from firm initiatives, such as the regional television and broadcasting service (MDR) which stimulated the co-location of media-related companies. But also, the specific socio-economic embeddedness in “specialized local resources, skills and shared trust, norms, routines and other local institutional structures [e.g. higher education and training programmes and incubators]”

(BATHELT, 2002, p. 587) is emphasized as a source of regional competitiveness and growth which clearly goes beyond the impact of organizational routines at the micro level.

With respect to institutions, scholars who wish to integrate GPE into EEG do not differ significantly from the outlined arguments of REG since both highlight the importance of institutions in the understanding of ‘old’ institutionalism² (MACKINNON et al., 2009).

However, the approaches might differ in the *scope* of institutions perceived as relevant for explaining the evolution of economic landscapes. A relational approach, in contrast to GPE, tends to be less preoccupied with certain categories of relevant institutions or actors, which is reinforced by the next two points closely connected to the concept of institutions.

REG considers human agency to be enabled and constrained by wide institutional structures, thus enhancing the scope of influences on individual behaviour beyond intra-firm processes, rules and practices. Economic decisions are thought to be generally path dependent and context-specific (BATHELT and GLÜCKLER, 2003, p. 127) and the presence *or* absence of institutions is assumed to influence economic behaviour, for instance in terms of creating and maintaining business networks (MURPHY, 2003) or shaping transnational business practices (JONES, 2008). At the same time, however, both, REG and EEG deny a structure-oriented perspective which strictly determines economic outcomes by the macro-institutional environment. Instead, REG is argued to represent parts of “midrange theoretical themes“ (YEUNG, 2005, p. 39) because it provides a balanced view of structure and agency where identical structural preconditions do not necessarily have the *same* effects at any time and place (BATHELT and GLÜCKLER 2003, p. 127) but might vary according to specific conditions (contingency).

REG has been heavily criticised, particularly with respect to its struggle to explain broader social and institutional structures in contrast to mere description of constituting network

relations (SUNLEY, 2008; YEUNG, 2002, p. 13). YEUNG's (2005) notion of 'power geometries' (originally developed by MASSEY, 1991) may provide promising means to address this limitation (BOGGS and RANTISI, 2003, p. 114). Economic change and spatial differences of economic outcomes are explained by different degrees of power inscribed in three dimensions of relationality, namely actor-structure, socio-spatial and scalar relationality (YEUNG, 2005, p. 43). Within them, firms are considered to be exposed to specific tensions which lead to different strategies, practices and firm behaviour as a whole, even if they are objectively involved in the same situation. For instance, being integrated into local business networks does not sufficiently explain the success or failure of firms per se; further analysis is required regarding the importance of extra-local linkages and the position within the production network in order to scrutinize the role of local, regional, national and global dimensions of scalar relationality (YEUNG, 2005, p. 43). Outsourcing production processes, for instance, is linked to the wider project of capital accumulation and political regulation as proposed by GPE and regulation theory but also, cultural, organisational and spatial proximities may play roles in re-organising firm structures. By analysing tensions between the political, economic, social and spatial dimension of socio-spatial relationality (YEUNG, 2005, p. 43), a tool is provided to reveal power relations causing distinct spatial outcomes of economic organisation.

Due to the consideration of a variety of actors and institutions, REG broadens the range of institutions influencing regional development at a variety of scales. In contrast to primarily reasoning economic evolution and transformation from the micro-level of firms, REG stresses the *interdependencies* of factors on local, regional, national and global scales as well as the *embeddedness* of individual agents in multiple networks (BOGGS and RANTISI, 2003; YEUNG, 2005). However, this does not mean to "dissolve scalar units into long chains of networks and spatial relations" which has been convincingly criticised by SUNLEY (2008, p. 15) but to be more sceptical towards scale. A relational perspective helps to avoid the fallacy of EEG to

conceptualise institutions and the formation of economic landscape as mere reflections and outcomes of organisational routines within this region (PIKE et al., 2009, p. 178). This is seen as problematic for two reasons: First, informed by the embeddedness concept, “microentities [such as firms] are never isolated atoms but are shaped and evaluated by their meso- and macroenvironments. Any explanation that focuses only on one level is reductionist and incomplete” (ESSLETZBICHLER, 2009, p. 162).

Secondly, even if the firm is a preferred level of analysis, a relational approach would question the supposedly homogenous, conflict-free and self-contained entity of agency implied by the current treatment of firms in EEG. Instead, REG reveals them as intersections of associated individuals who are involved in numerous networks within and across company boundaries, e.g. conceptualized as communities of practice, with each following their own logic and providing individuals with different access to resources and capabilities of power (BOGGS and RANTISI, 2003, p. 112; ETTLINGER, 2003). Accordingly, in order to explain the success of firms and regions, the focus should be shifted from firm-centred organisational routines to actors’ networks and interrelations (DICKEN et al., 2001, p. 89; BOGGS and RANTISI, 2003, p. 114), resulting in no prioritization of a specific scale per se.

Although such a broad and unspecified understanding of relations and networks might seem problematic at first sight (who and which institutions should be included and excluded from the analysis? (SUNLEY, 2008, p. 8)), we sympathize with the notion of openness in REG towards the factors that influence economic outcome for three reasons.

First, since research questions themselves are context dependent, starting with too strict definitions and assumptions is seen as problematic (BATHELT and GLÜCKLER, 2011). In fact, REG is not seen as a theory but a novel way to help to formulate research questions different from those in traditional research in regional science, yielding different answers.

Secondly, the openness also makes it easier to acknowledge, as is done in REG, processes of both downward and upward causation. This is particularly stressed concerning the influence of institutions. REG "... includes individual and collective agents, the economic practices and relations in which they engage, and the role of social institutions at different scales" and favours "a conception of institutions that acknowledges both upward and downward causation processes" (BATHELT and GLÜCKLER, 2011, p. 45, 62). Institutions are seen as important mediators between micro and macro and between local and global scales of analysis. Institutions are shaped both in a top-down (mainly stressed by GPE) and bottom-up (mainly stressed by EEG) manner.

Thirdly and related to the above-mentioned reasons, this openness makes it relatively easy to use explanatory notes from REG in neighbouring paradigms such as EEG. It facilitates translation and trading zones and hence engaged pluralism.

To sum up, REG is a meta-conceptualization for formulating research questions and conducting research in economic geography (BATHELT and LI, 2014). It includes both a structural (economic action is embedded in context) and evolutionary (economic action is path dependent) component and "focuses on a relational understanding of economic action which is analysed in spatial perspective" (BATHELT and GLÜCKLER, 2011, p. 6). It offers interesting explanatory ideas that could compensate for the weaknesses of EEG concerning theorizing power, social agency and multi-scalar impacts on the formation of economic landscapes.

4. Conclusion

The paper started with a conceptual overview of EEG and presented its main criticisms with respect to institutions, power, social agency and the interrelatedness of influences at different spatial scales. EEG has strived to become the new dominant paradigm in economic geography; it has some clear conceptual notions and research foci to explain key empirical phenomena in economic geography (HASSINK and KLAERDING, 2009). The paper therefore clearly brings the discussion about EEG forward by giving an additional solution, other than the GPE approach proposed by MACKINNON et al. (2009) and PIKE et al. (2009), to eliminate the identified conceptual shortcomings of EEG. We advocate a stronger engagement with both institutional economic geography and a selective relational perspective to complement EEG (see also BATHELT and LI, 2014) because it provides a better approach for comprehensively theorizing power, social agency and particularly multi-scalar impacts on the formation of economic landscapes.

In our view, REG and IEG are particularly strong in explaining important phenomena in economic geography, such as knowledge transfer, production networks, supply chains and money flows which place emphasis on actor-network relations. Both, together with EEG, are argued to be capable of being combined rather easily, with these different approaches showing only subtle differences (HASSINK and KLAERDING, 2009), mainly with respect to their fundamental disciplinary influences: whereas REG and IEG have strong links to economic sociology, EEG is heavily based on evolutionary economics (SCHAMP, 2007). But this is seen as an advantage rather than a barrier to conceptual exchange because it allows considering complementary influences, e.g. scope of institutions, on economic evolution.

To be clear, complementing EEG with these two perspectives does not mean that we propose an alternative paradigm. We rather intend to advance economic geography in order to meet today's and tomorrow's research challenges of economic geography. With our paper we facilitate *theoretical continuity* instead of provoking shifting and short-lived paradigmatic commitments caused by criticism and the rise of new ideas from neighbouring social sciences which has been generally observed by AMIN (2001, p. 1238) and GRABHER (2009) in economic geography. This does not mean that we advocate a complacent or static approach to conceptual development, but rather that we propose building on existing theories, instead of asking for another redefinition of the whole discipline.

Combining complementary theoretical perspectives, as has been recently done by MACKINNON (2012) linking global production networks, strategic coupling and EEG, underlines '*engaged pluralism*' which is contrary to fragmented pluralism in economic geography (BARNES and SHEPPARD, 2010; CLARE and SIEMIATYCKI, 2014). The divisions between EEG and Marxist political economy, on the one hand, and EEG and institutional economic geography, on the other hand, "presents evolutionary economic geography as self-sustaining and autonomous but at the cost of setting up 'us' against 'them'" (BARNES and SHEPPARD, 2010, p. 204). Fragmented pluralism which is arguably necessary to constitute a new paradigm at the beginning, crucially limits the opportunities for cross-fertilisation (MACKINNON et al., 2009, p. 130) which can be inspiring for progressing paradigms such as EEG. Hence, in line with MACKINNON et al. (2009) and GRABHER (2009) we advocate EEG as a pluralistic project which is open to engage with relational perspectives, or others, that may be discussed in the future.

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Notes

¹ Please note that, in order to be clearly laid out, Figure 1 illustrates only main theoretical links between disciplines which are thought to be relevant for this paper. Particularly the conceptual contributions from economics (top row of Figure 1) are considered.

² Old 'institutionalism' refers to the work of authors such as POLANYI (2001), who described market formation and development as being strongly embedded in a particular political, economic and social context. This term has sometimes been used in contrast to 'new institutionalism' that tends to focus on 'softer' institutions, such as networks, knowledge and trust (MACLEOD 2001).

Figure 1: The pedigree of theories of economic geography and related disciplines¹

Source: authors' design, inspired by SCOTT, 2000 and SCHAMP, 2007

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